

Preliminary Experiment to Analyze Behavior of Angkot Based on Transportation Data

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Abstract— Public transportation in Indonesia as a developing country differs from developed country, and there is a certain public transportation called Angkot (Angkutan Kota, or City Transport), which became the focus of our research. This paper presents the results of preliminary experiments on data transportation to analyze behavior of angkot. The focus is on discussing the results of experiments to calculate the length of waiting time for angkot at hotspots and clustering of angkot trips patterns using Principal component analysis and K-Means. The experiment stage begins from the process of data cleaning, preprocessing and implementing models for trips patterns. The results of the review and experiment indicate the length of the time needed for angkot in waiting for the passengers and show which angkot that exceeds the normal time limit set by the government in waiting for the passengers, which suggests a deviant behavior. The results for clustering angkot that have similar trips patterns using PCA and K-Means give fairly high accuracy.

Keywords—Behavior, Big Data Analysis, K-Means, PCA, Trips Pattern, Waiting Time

I. INTRODUCTION

Angkot, Indonesian city transportation, is one of the most common types of public transportation. That is because its rates are relatively cheap and affordable by most people. This type of public transportation is a vehicle that dominates the transportation in Bandung city. In 2017, there were 5521 angkot in Bandung [1]. However, angkot is considered to be one of the causes of the traffic jam. Based on the results of a survey conducted by CIRUS Surveyors Group and Tim Visi Indonesia 2033, a number of factors causing traffic jam were found. One of the contributing factors is angkot that carelessly stops at the roadside which then causes the traffic jam [2].

Over the past few decades, global positioning system (GPS) technology has been widely used to collect large-scale data for trips surveys. The data used for this study is the transportation data of angkot obtained from Pusat Penelitian Teknologi Informasi dan Komunikasi (PPTIK, or Research Center for Information Technology and Communication) which has 14 million GPS angkot history data. The data is taken from the GPS Tracker installed on every city transportation in Bandung. This large angkot GPS data

collection can be analyzed to be a value. As it has been acknowledged in the big data trend, the data must be able to be processed into a knowledge that can be useful for humans. This knowledge can help humans to estimate and predict what will happen in the future, conduct analysis and assist in decision and policy making.

Based on transportation service regulations, angkot is prohibited from passing the road network other than those specified in the route permit and the average waiting time for stops is 5-10 minutes, and a maximum of 10-20 minutes [3]. To make sure that angkot is more disciplined and can be monitored, it is necessary to develop a model scheme to detect angkot that has anomaly behavior. In this study, we are interested in analyzing transportation data to be able to build models that can detect anomaly behavior of angkot. However, there are several parameters that must be obtained to indicate the angkot anomaly behavior. To obtain these parameters, it is necessary to conduct further data analysis before modeling to detect the anomaly behavior.

In this paper, we focus on discussing preliminary experiments on data transportation to analyze behavior of Indonesian public transportation (angkot) only to calculate the length of time an angkot stops at a hotspot and classifies their trips patterns. The clustering of angkot trips pattern utilizes machine learning method namely K-means clustering and uses the Principal Component Analysis method for dimension reduction. This experiment needed for future to build a model to detect anomaly behavior of angkot.

II. RELATED WORKS

In the preliminary stage of our research, we studied the literature on behavior analysis especially for transportation. There have been many studies that discuss the behavior of transportation modes. Machine learning methods with potential applications in travel behaviour analysis and modelling. That research use a random forest method to identifying trip purposes and travel modes using a longitudinal GPS dataset from Japan [4][5]. Moreover for instance, studying personal car trips behavior based on the analysis of trajectories. The research investigated the effects of aggregation through grouping trajectories with the aim of modeling private car trips patterns. Seeing the pattern of

private car trips using the TAD algorithm was to determine the areas that often appeared in certain time intervals and analyze the regularity of the trips of each private car based on its track cluster [6]. Machine learning approach can be used to travel behavior analysis. Different measures regarding the variability of travel behaviors of transit users were proposed. Another study had developed techniques for detecting abnormal behavior in public areas using the extraction of moving object trajectories in a video [7]. Another one had made the detection of abnormal behavior for UAVs using RNN and had fairly good accuracy results [8]. Furthermore, there was also a research which detected abnormal driving by analyzing normalized driving behavior [9]. The proposed scheme was effective in detecting abnormal driving, but was limited to longitudinal driving only. To detect abnormal driving which aimed at increasing driver awareness about their driving habits so as to prevent potential car accidents. This study identified specific types of abnormal driving behavior, namely Weaving, Swerving, Sideslipping, Fast U- turn, Turning with a wide radius and Sudden braking. The classic algorithm used was SVM and D³ achieved an average total accuracy of 95.36%. [10]. Another study had Evaluating the driving force quantitatively was to detect abnormal driving behavior [11].

There is still broad scope for research that detects anomaly behavior in public transportation. In this preliminary research, we then decided to analyze the behavior of angkot only to calculate the length of time an angkot stops at a hotspot and classifies their trips patterns. However, this paper was only clustering to classify angkot that has a similarity pattern. The clustering algorithm is one of the most commonly used methods in the field of user abnormal behaviour detection[12]. Clustering can be used for identifying patterns to characterize driving human driving styles[13]. A division of data into group of similar objects. Each group, or cluster, consists of objects that are similar to one another and dissimilar to objects in other groups [14][15].

III. METHOD

In conducting this Preliminary experiment, we used transportation data of angkot from PPTIK. The dataset contains the following information:

TABLE I. THE INFORMATION ABOUT DATASET

Field	Note
ID	Id number of angkot
Devicetime	The time of positioning
Latitude	Latitude position of angkot
Longitude	Longitude position of angkot
Servertime	The time in server
Speed	The instantaneous speed of the vehicle

There were several steps in the process:

A. Data Cleaning

Before conducting the data analysis, the data cleaning process must be done. The purpose of data cleaning is to get data whose value is really valid. This is done to obtain the

actual results of the data analysis. The things done in the data cleaning process are as follows:

- Removing duplicate data
- Limiting the coordinates to Bandung area only
- Replacing data errors in 2000 servertime

B. Determine the hotspot point where the angkot stop and calculate the waiting time of the angkot at the hotspot

The waiting duration of angkot can be calculated through several preprocessing stages. The steps to get a position and length of time are mentioned as follows:

- Converting data from devicetime to datetime format to facilitate data processing in time series.
- Making a function to calculate speed from distance and time equations. Experiments were carried out using euclidian distance to get the distance from 2 points latitude and longitude.
- Making a function to fill the NaN data that was filled with the value 0.
- The function of waiting was made to determine whether the angkot waited based on the function created. If the value is below the data threshold, the angkot stop is considered true. The regulation of the Directorate General of Land Transportation in 2002 becomes the reference to determine the waiting time of angkot that the average duration of waiting is 5-10 minutes and the maximum is 10-20 minutes [3].
- Showing hotspots that became the most popular locations to wait and calculate the time there

C. Clustering Angkot Trips Pattern

In this experiment, we used clustering to look for angkot trips patterns.

1) K-Means Clustering and Principal Component Analysis

As we know, K-means clustering algorithm is one of the classic clustering algorithms, but currently many researchers are making improvements to the most classical K-means clustering method. This algorithm is widely used to analyze user behavior and the performance of this algorithm is considered to be greatly improved. [6] The points set where vehicle stayed has spatial aggregation. We use K-Means for clustering angkot trips patterns which will later be grouped into classes that have similar route patterns. The K-means algorithm is as follows:

- Determining k as the number of clusters
- Determining k centroid
- Calculating the distance of each data to each centroid. We use Euclidian formula for calculating the distance.
- Grouping objects according to minimum distance
- Determining the new centroid by calculating the average of the data chosen in the same centroid. Is the object moved to another cluster?
- If the new centroid position with the old centroid is not the same

PCA is one of the optimization methods that aims to reduce the attributes before the data is processed which can later affect the centroid determination. The selection

of cluster points with PCA using PCA sub spaces is much smaller than the original space. There are many advantages of doing dimension reduction because dimension reduction can eliminate irrelevant features and reduce noise. PCA is able to eliminate information redundancy from data sets caused by several variables measured in the same or related order [16]. PCA can reduce high data to lower data dimensions with very little risk of loss. Therefore, we use PCA and K-means to determine the pattern of angkot trips. The stages to determine the pattern of angkot trips can be seen in the following figure:

Fig. 1. The stages to clustering angkot trips pattern

IV. RESULT

A. Experiment Results to Calculate the Waiting Time Period of angkot

In this experiment, sample data on February 4, 2018 was given to see angkot waiting time at the hotspot. The following are the results of the experiments:

Fig. 2. ID 5 waiting time at hotspot

Fig. 3. ID 8 waiting time at hotspot

Fig. 4. ID 6 waiting time at hotspot

Fig. 5. ID 5 waiting time at hotspot

Fig. 6. ID 3 waiting time at hotspot

From the results of exploration using data samples from February 4, 2018 carried out above, the following results were obtained:

TABLE II. WAITING TIME IN HOTSPOT

Id Angkot	Waiting Time In Hotspot
4	1:14:52 second
8	3: 22: 31 second
12	0:16:59 second
5	2:08:22 second
6	1:44:12 second
3	0:35:48 second

The above results indicate that, referring to the regulation of the Director General of Land Transportation in 2002, angkot are not allowed to wait for more than 10-20 minutes [3]. If it exceeds the predetermined time, we assume it is considered an abnormal behavior. From these results, angkot ID 4,8,5,6, and 3 show abnormal behavior since they exceed the predetermined wait time

B. Results of experiments to clustering angkot trip patterns using PCA and K-Means Algorithm

In this experiment, plotting is done to see the route pattern of the public transportation.

Fig. 7. Plotting sample pattern trip of angkot

The pattern above shows that there are several angkot IDs that have a similar pattern. To classify public transportation patterns, clustering will be conducted.

Before conducting clustering, the data will be reduced using PCA to analyze its main components. By using PCA, variables that were as many as n variables will be reduced to k new variables (principal component) with the number of k less than n and by only using k principal component will produce the same value using n variables [17].

In its implementation, the data is separated into input data and output data with x values consisting of id data and time data (years to minutes), while the output data consists of longitude and latitude data. Next thing to do is to determine the first and last time in the dataset. Because the time data for each dataset is different, dataframe aggregation is made based on the time at 1 minute interval with the same initial and final values. The blank data will be filled with the last known location, and then the distribution of historical data is made based on the

location visited. To ensure that the data can be processed in the form of PCA, a dataframe format must be performed. Each variable must be in a different column to create a format that matches the PCA input format. In the PCA, settings are made so that 95% of information remains stored on the data frame. The following are the results of experiments using PCA which show that much information is stored on PCA based on the value of variance. There are 8 Principal components that represent 95% of data.

Fig. 8. Variability

Fig. 9. Eight (8) principal components

After reducing the dimensions of the dataset using PCA, the next step was the clustering stage. The following are the results of the clustering process:

explained variance

5	-1.
1	1.
0	2.
6	-6.
2	-4.
3	-5.
4	42.
7	-0.
8	-2.
10	-5.
9	-5.
11	-5.
12	-5.
13	-4.

Fig. 10. the results of the clustering

Clustering results can be seen from the two main Principal Components namely pc1 and pc2.

Fig. 11. Clustering results from two main Principal Components

Angkot are grouped in each class that has the same trips pattern. From the results of the experiments conducted, the number of clusters formed was 13 classes. Using K = 13 mean to centroid was close. The closer it is to the centroid, the higher the level of similarity is.

The next experiment append route data taken from the open data of Bandung into dataframe. Open data of bandung is One of Bandung City Government's initiative and commitment is to distribute data that can be used freely at Open Data programme. In the Open data of bandung there are variety of data, one of them is the angkot route data. It is contains the ID angkot and route name. In this paper, we use the route data to support our experiments for comparing predicted class of angkot trip patterns with true class. Here are the results:

id	Predictions	True_Class
3	Abdul Muis to Ledeng	Abdul Muis to Ledeng
4	Abdul Muis to Ledeng	Abdul Muis to Ledeng
5	Cicaheum to Ledeng	Cicaheum to Ledeng
6	Cicaheum to Ciroyom	Cicaheum to Ciroyom
7	Cicaheum to Ciwastra	Cicaheum to Ciwastra
8	Cicaheum to Cibaduyut	Cicaheum to Cibaduyut
9	St Hall to Dago	St Hall to Dago
11	St Hall to Ciumbeluit	St Hall to Ciumbeluit
12	St Hall to Gede Bage	St Hall to Gede Bage
13	St Hall to Sarijadi	St Hall to Sarijadi
15	Dago to Riung Bandung	Margahayu raya to ledeng
16	Dago to Riung Bandung	Dago to Riung Bandung
18	Panghegar permai to dipatiukur	Panghegar permai to dipatiukur
19	Ciroyom to Sarijadi	Ciroyom to Sarijadi

Fig. 12. The result of predictions angkot trip pattern

The results of clustering experiments with PCA and K-Means on angkot data showed a fairly high accuracy around 93%. That is because almost one class has only one to two data ID.

Grouping trips patterns in a class will facilitate the next process to detect angkot behavior that exits its route. Law Number 22 Year 2009 concerning Road Traffic and Transport (LLAJ Law) Article 126 of the LLAJ Law explains that public transportation is prohibited from passing road networks other than those specified in the route permit [18]. Therefore, we assume that the angkot behavior that exits the route is an abnormal behavior.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The first preliminary experiment. The results of the experiment showed that angkot ID 4,8,5,6, and 3 indicated abnormal behavior since they waited for the passangers until they exceeded the time determined by the government. The government made a regulation that angkot was not allowed to wait for more than a maximum of 10-20 minutes. If it exceeded the allotted time, then it was considered a violation and an abnormal behavior.

The second preliminary experiment. Before conducting a travel pattern clustering, the data was reduced to obtain the main components using the PCA method. In the PCA, settings were made so that 95% of information remained stored on the dataframe. The result showed that there were 8 Principal components. From the results of clustering experiments for grouping of angkot trips patterns, the number of clusters formed was 13 classes. The results showed a fairly high level of accuracy of around 93%. From the summary above, we conclude that the results of the experiments conducted can be a parameter to determine the anomaly behavior of angkot.

For future work, we will further explore the results of the clustering above to determine the angkot that change trajectories. In addition, we will also conduct further analysis of the data to get other parameters which indicate anomaly behavior of angkot. Therefore, from the results of these explorations, in the future, we will build a model to detect anomaly behavior of angkot. It is expected that the model that will be developed later on can be used not only for angkot data but also for other transportation data.

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